

INSPIRE Focus Group 2 Questions

- Starting from the beginning of the program to now, can you describe how your team has evolved?
 - *How did the dynamic of your team change over time?*
 - *How did your performance change alongside changes in the dynamics?*
- How would you describe your experience working directly with stakeholders? (Community Engagement)
- How has your MVP development experience evolved over the course of the program?
- What is your opinion on the MVP that you have developed? Do you think you were able to capture the user's needs?
- What is your community partner's feedback on the MVP?
- How was this experience different from a course?
- Has your teamwork experience impacted your opinion of working in STEM fields?
- How would you describe your experience as a self-organized team?

